

Data Foundation and Terminology Work Group Products Maintenance and Retirement plan.

Maintenance of the DFT products, particularly the Term list as in the term tool is proposed to go forward by establishment of a [DFT IG](#). This is currently under community review. This process would also update and add to the Analysis and Synthesis document as wider areas of data management and organization are covered as part of RDA groups as well as the adoption process of current products. Sessions to discuss these are planned at future plenaries and virtual meetings in between plenaries. More extensive discussions are planned with the various RDA communities to support development and approval of definitions and any announcement of retirement of outdated definitions that are superseded by more recent and comprehensive work.